

Article

Youth participation in Indian elections*

Anirban Banerjee**

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8286812

Abstract

The present paper examines the role of Indian youth in electoral politics. It analyses why Indian youth are averse to political participation and what can be done to make them active partners in India's democratic system.

Key words: Youth, elections, politics, vote, voter.

Introduction

India gained Independence on 15th August, 1947. Since then our country has been recognized as the largest democracy in the world. Unlike many newly independent states in Asia and Africa, like Pakistan, Myanmar, Egypt, Liberia, etc., where democracy was repeatedly eclipsed, or not allowed to strike roots at all, India has remained a vibrant democracy since Independence. One reason for this vibrancy of Indian democracy is the

* The article is a revised version of an Invited Lecture

delivered at the Bangshagopal Town Hall, Burdwan, on 25th

January, 2012, on occasion of National Voters Day.

**The author is at present Professor of Sociology at The University of Burdwan. His can be contacted at anirban_2banerjee1961@yahoo.co.uk

legacy of the Indian Freedom Movement. The Indian Freedom Movement witnessed mass participation in the many political agitations. Even before the Freedom Movement took shape, enlightened British rulers, like the British Viceroy Lord Ripon, took steps to train Indians for self government. Later, Indians were granted limited autonomy in the Government of India Act (1919) which introduced the concept of 'dyarchy' or dual government. Under this act, certain departments were to be governed by Indian ministers while the major ones were kept by the Viceroy. Under the Government of India Act (1935), elections were held and the Indian National Congress formed governments in the majority of the provinces.

The adoption of the new Constitution of India on 26th November, 1949 and the proclamation of India as a Republic on 26th January, 1950 heralded the age of Universal Adult Suffrage in India. By 'suffrage' is meant the right to vote. By 'Universal Adult Suffrage' is meant that an adult person is entitled to vote without any consideration of wealth, class, religion, race, or gender. The evolution of the concept of suffrage, took place for centuries. It was only in the sixteenth century that the idea of suffrage developed. But till the middle of the nineteenth century some sort of property qualification was there. The French introduced 'Universal Male Suffrage' in 1793. In Great Britain it was introduced in 1918. But women had to struggle relentlessly for getting the right to vote. Universal Adult Suffrage was introduced in Great Britain in 1928, in USA in 1965 and in Switzerland in 1971. Thus, as far as Universal Adult Suffrage is concerned, India was far in advance of some of the modern democracies, like Switzerland and United States of America. .

Profile of Indian Youth

The objective of the present lecture is to discuss the role of Indian youth in the electoral process. Prior to this discussion, let us first examine the characteristics of Indian youth today. Youth may be defined as people aged between 15-

24 years. India is a young nation. Median age of Indians is 24.1 years. The following are the major characteristics of Indian youths.

According to 2001 Census, out of 1029 million people, 195 million (18.95%) are youths. High illiteracy: 31% of young women and 14% of young men are illiterate.

41% of adolescents aged 15-17 years attended school in the school year 2005-06.

Media exposure: Most youths are exposed to media like television, radio, etc.

Gender roles: Youth attitudes to gender roles are no more egalitarian than that of age group 25-49. "Thus the preparation of youth for the challenges of nation building is very limited", observe Sulabh Parasuraman, Sunita Kishore, Shri Kant Singh, Y. Vaidehi, in their study prepared for the Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Government of India. (Parasuraman, 2009)

Views on Youth Participation in Politics

Some political observers are of the view that youths are not participating in politics to the desired extent. Noted sociologist, Y.B. Damle, distinguished between 'student youth' and non-student youth. He noted that for the student youth, the pressure of career and the desire for prestigious jobs make them impervious to an ideology which requires understanding and action. The non-student youth are so much preoccupied with making a living that for them also ideology based political action is not possible. (Damle, 1989). Many political observers in the 21st century would agree with Damle's assessment. Thus Latha Narayan, an academican, holds that "The youth have opted to compromise rather than fight injustice. Their energies are mainly spent in the 'self-survival' process rather than in building the nation."ii She further observes that politics is equated with unfair power games, and hence, a significant number of the youth shun it. In the broadest sense of the term, political action is the

process of change being guided by a political understanding of social realities. Imran Khan, a popular actor in Bollywood, virtually echoes her. "Young people want to bring in change but they feel their voices are bound to get lost in the political rhetoric. They prefer to opt out rather than be a part of the same structure."iii

All observers, however do not agree with the view that youth are politically apathetic. Thus, Manisha Natarajan claims that in the 5.5 lakh panchayats in rural areas, several lakh young men and women are serving as office bearers in various capacities like panch, sarpanch, etc. Seventy percent of them are below the age of 35. So, there is no substance in the allegation that youth are apathetic to politics. She further observes: "Surely that is evidence enough to show that the young are interested in entering the system to change their village communities? If the urban young are apathetic about politics it is largely because of the system's penchant for political institutions, the closed-door functioning of political outfits and the special status given to politicians. These are all negative factors and breed revulsion among ordinary people"iv.

What the Youth Say

Let us now examine the views of the youth. How do they view their role in elections?

To be fair to the youth, some of them have minced no words in criticizing their political apathy. Thus, Mahipal Singh, a student of International Tourism, wrote in a blog: "I have always seen youth talking about corrupt politicians, even I do. But, what about joining politics? We just have 17% of youth politicians in India. The number of MP's in the age group of 25-40 is just 71 out of 545. These statistics don't allow us to complain against the oldies." vRohit Jain, another youngster, observed in a blog: "The country desperately needs some young leaders who personify energy, enthusiasm, morality, and diligence. No doubt we have progressed a lot in the last 62 years but the

development pace would have been completely different had some young torchbearers led this process of development”vi.

Before the elections to the Tamil Nadu Assembly, The Times of India interviewed a cross-section of voters. One of them, Sabina Rani, a student of Stella Maris, said: “I have always keenly followed political proceedings in the state and finally I get to participate in the process. But I am still confused about which party to vote for.” viiFrom these views, we find that youth themselves are divided regarding their role in politics. But they recognize the need for young leaders who can take the country forward.

Participation of Indian Youth in Elections

Studies done on the voting behavior of Indians have claimed that the participation of youth in elections is lower than normal. Thus the Centre for Studies of Developing Societies claims that though “the youth constitute a sizeable number of voters, their participation in Indian elections is lower compared to adult voters....” viiiWe find that the young are playing a less important role in public life.

Table No. 1 : The presence of young MP's in Lok Sabha has gone down:

Year of Lok Sabha election	Number of MP's below 40 years of age (Young M.P)
1952	140
1957	164
1962	109
1967	127
1971	106
1977	105
1980	117

Year of Lok Sabha election	Number of MP's below 40 years of age (Young M.P)
1984	112
1989	93
1991	105
1996	102
1998	65
1999	78
2004	61

Source: CSDS Data Unit

From Table 1 we find that the number of young MPs in the Lok Sabha has gone down .In the first elected Parliament (1952) we find that the number of young MPs totaled 140.This increased to 164 in 1957.Therafter the number of young MPs declined. In 1989, the number of young MPs declined to 93 and in 2004, it declined to 61.This puzzling electoral behaviour of our youth calls for an explanation. I think that in the first few decades since Independence, there was a marked sense of idealism in the youth. Jawaharlal Nehru gave the country a goal-to build a socialistic pattern of society. Politics was not viewed as a profession. Many young people thought of serving the country through political participation.

But with the advent of globalization in the 1990s, India was forced to toe the IMF line. The advent of neo-liberalism based market economics in India led to the death of the socialistic pattern of society Nehru envisaged. With the demise of the socialistic model, ideology also died. As a result politics began to be seen as a power game, of intrigue, chicanery, manipulation, jockeying for positions. This had a deleterious impact on the political options of our youth. As a result, youths became more career conscious and thought less about joining politics.

Let us now analyze the situation in 2009.

Fig.1.State wise distribution of the 71 Young MPs in present parliament (2009)

Source: AS-CSDS study on youth in Indian politics

Fig.2 Composition of urban voters in India

Graphics: Getting Ready for the Digital Elections by Sourav Pandey.

We find in Fig.1 that the highest number of young MPs came from Uttar Pradesh (22%).Maharashtra has the second highest number of Young MPs (12%) .The rest of the country is far behind these two states as far as the numbers of young MPs are concerned. We should be especially concerned about West Bengal, which accounts for a bare 5% of young MPs.All political parties in West Bengal should make an effort to send the maximum number of young leaders to Parliament.

In a recently held workshop on 'Systematic Voters' Education and Electoral Participation' (SVEEP) on 13th December, 2011, the Chief Election Commissioner, Y.S. Qureshi, observed that there was an urgent need to overcome hindrances to voter participation like youth indifference, gender gap, urban apathy and enrolling the weaker sections. The Commission was, therefore, adopting Social Marketing strategies for focused intervention, which were also cost-effective. Quraishi underlined the importance of forging a close partnership with media departments and youth & education organizations for achieving maximum participation. Retired Chief Electoral Officer Kumar Anshumali observed, in a workshop in Magadh Mahila College, Patna :“The youths must understand that they should vote and put pressure on future governments to look into their issues and redress their grievances.”x According to the last Census, youths belonging to the age groups of 18-19 years and 19-20 years account for the country’s six per cent population. “But barely 1.5 per cent of them vote. This has to be changed at any cost,” Anshumali saidxi

Voting Behaviour of Youth

Empirical evidence supports the CEC’s view. From Fig.2 we find that 36% of the urban voters are youths How many of them vote? From Fig.3 we find that only 9% of the young urban voters vote. This is really a sorry state of affairs that needs to be changed if our democracy is to thrive.

Fig.3 Voting Behaviour Among Urban Youth
Graphics: Getting Ready for the Digital Elections by Sourav Pandey.

The India Today-JUXT Report (2008) reported that only 9% of the urban voters actually voted. (See Fig.3)

But in a vast country like India, statistical uniformities may be misleading. I had conducted a small exploratory study on political attitudes and behaviour of educated youths in Burdwan University in 2011. There I found that out of 51 Sociology students, who answered the questionnaires, 48 (94.18%), voted in the last West Bengal Assembly elections (2011). This finding does not tally with the results of all India studies conducted by Centre for Studies of Developing Societies or the India Today – JUXT Report (2008).

Strategies Adopted to Increase Youth Participation in Elections

Faced with the declining participation of youth in the electoral process, an effort is now being made by the Election Commission and the government, educational institutions and civil society groups to increase youth participation in elections.

1) The Election Commission has taken the following steps.

The Election Commission is proposing to reduce the voting age from 18 to 16 years.

The Election Commission has also distributed Form 6 among students in schools and colleges for enrolling first time voters. On National Voters Day (25th January, 2012), the Chief Electoral Officer of West Bengal, Sunil Gupta, said that forms for voter registration in schools and colleges will be available for one month from 1st February, 2012. The aim of the Election Commission is to enroll more young voters. xii

The Election Commission has also decided to reach out to young voters through social networks like Facebook and Twitter.

The Election Commission has decided to observe January 25 each year as National Voters Day. On this day, new voters will be felicitated and given a badge containing the message "Proud to be a voter. Ready to Vote". Voters will also have to take the following pledge:

"We, the citizens of India, having faith in democracy, hereby pledge to uphold the democratic traditions of our country and the dignity of free, fair, and peaceful elections and to vote in every election fearlessly and without being influenced by considerations of religion, race, caste, community, language, or any inducement" xiii.

To impress upon voters the need to vote, for the first time in its history, the Election Commission participated in the Republic Day Parade on 26th January, 2012 with a float that depicted its 63 year old journey from a fledgling panel under the leadership of noted mathematician, Sukumar Sen to the present day. The tableau depicted the entire voting process with the Parliament in the background and voters queuing up to vote through the electronic voting machine. It may be noted in this connection that the Election Commission does not merely organize elections in India. It also offers its expertise to several countries. xiv

2) The Central Government is asking the states to introduce online voting in municipal elections. This is a new procedure, which was tried out, in the municipal elections in Gandhinagar. Here 1500 voters registered to vote via the Internet and 1000 voted. xv

3) College authorities are also doing their bit to increase youth participation in polls. Apart from organizing voter registration camps, elite colleges like St. Xavier's College, Mumbai, are inviting

NGOs, and political parties to make presentations before their students.

4) Corporate houses are also making an effort to politically socialize the youth. We may mention the “Jaagore! One Billion Votes campaign” by Tata Tea. It is mainly targeted at the youth. It aims at nationwide registration of voters, especially youth and makes them participate in the electoral process. The website, www.jaagore.com, is designed to be a portal which facilitates free flow of information and resources and organizations by bringing together, into a common platform those who possess information and those who need them. The website has two key sections. Jaago and Jaagao. Jaago is the information section. It contains information related to elections, political parties, etc. Jaagao is the engagement section of the website. Here individuals and organizations can register and create a profile.^{xvi}

5) Voluntary organizations are contributing their mite.

Society for Participatory Research conducted a pre-election awareness campaign in India in 2006. The aim of a pre-election awareness campaign is to sensitize voters about the importance of participating in the electoral process as a way to ensure a responsive, accountable, and a democratically elected government.^{xvii}

The anti-poverty network, ‘Wada na Toro Abhiyan’ organized a ‘People’s Manifesto’ campaign on the eve of the 2009 elections. They published an All India People’s Manifesto. “We will not support any candidate who comes to us only for votes and is not seen for the rest of the term. We want a Member of Parliament who will walk alongside the people and is recognized by at least 50% of the constituency,” states the Local Manifesto from Mirzapur.^{xviii}

6) A government panel has proposed to make voting compulsory.^{xix} But the issue is highly controversial. The task force constituted by the

Panchayati Raj Ministry has recommended a fine of Rs.25/- on any voter who does not vote in the absence of disabling circumstances. The task force, headed by the ministry’s additional Secretary, Hrushikesh Panda, claimed that compulsory voting would encourage voters to research the candidate’s background. The panel claims that higher voting would reduce the influence of money power on election results.

But the proposal has been severely criticized.

The Chairman of the Bar Council claims that compulsory voting is not in accordance with the provisions of the Constitution of India.

Former Lok Sabha Secretary General, Subhas C. Kashyap, argued that instead of compulsory voting, it should be made a fundamental duty. Then there will be incentives and disincentives. For example, citizens wishing to acquire a ration card or a driving license should be asked to show proof of voting.

Activist Nikhil Dey argues: “Electoral reforms will not come by making voting compulsory; there has to be a political solution. Every citizen should be aware that the candidate he /she is electing, really represents them. The elected representatives will have to demonstrate a level of political maturity so that people will trust them”^{xx}.

Rozelle Laha observes “The whole meaning of the government shall be “for the people, of the people and by the people” will lose its meaning if people are forced to exercise their will. It is better if less number of well-informed people vote, rather than a huge number of uninformed people vote.^{xxii} agree with the critics that compulsory voting is not the solution for voter apathy. I think that this is against the spirit of democracy.

Recommendations for More Effective Youth Participation in Indian Elections

Youth are the future of our nation. We found that youth participation in Indian elections

is lower than normal. To improve participation, the election commission, governments, educational institutions, the corporate sector, and NGOs have taken some steps. These are laudable steps, steps in the right direction.

I suggest that some additional steps should be taken to ensure better youth participation in elections. These are as follows.

The Election Commission has rightly decided to recommend reduction of the voting age to 16 years. But mere reduction of the voting age is not enough. As we have seen, some first time voters are a confused lot. To get them to participate, I recommend that political education should start right from middle school (Class VI) onwards. Such education should be theoretical and also functional. For example, teachers and officials of the Election commission may demonstrate how easy it is to vote.

Officials of the Election Commission may visit schools and colleges and explain to the students why they should vote.

Schools and colleges can sponsor visits of highly respected people who can be counted upon to influence the youth. They can impress upon the youth the need for political participation.

I agree with those who argue that the Indian Constitution should be amended to include voting as a fundamental duty. We find that less than 50% of the voters take an interest in politics (Table No.2). Why voters have such low interest in politics should be thoroughly investigated. To counter voter apathy, regular awareness campaigns should be undertaken. The purpose behind these campaigns should be to instill in the voters the awareness that every vote counts and all citizens have a duty to protect our democracy.

Table No. 2: Interest in politics

Age Group	Who takes interest in Politics and Public affairs
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All Voters	38
Young Voters (18-25 years)	39
Between 26-35 years	40
Between 36-45 years	39
Between 46-55 years	38
Old above 56years	32

Source:

http://indiatoday.intoday.in/content_mail.php?option=com_content&name=print&id=32800

Note: All figures are in per cent Source: All India figure from Election Commission of India, turnout among young and adult from CSDS Surveys

Students' union elections should be held every year in colleges. This is because the union elections gives educated youth their first taste of democracy. They learn to vote .They also learn the art of political persuasion, leadership, of electioneering, and governance through student unions. Many of our political leaders have come from the student movement. Recently, in West Bengal outside political interference in student union elections has resulted in repeated political violence in colleges. I think that there should be a zero tolerance policy towards outside political interference in student union elections. Troublemakers should be firmly dealt with by the administration without any bias. If we wish to ensure that the educated youth feel comfortable about political participation, we should ensure that the students' union elections are held in a cordial atmosphere.

The Election Commission should highlight Section 49(O) of the Electoral Rules. According to this rule, a voter queues up to vote at the polling station, and gets his finger marked with indelible ink by polling official. But if he decides not to vote, he may inform the Presiding Officer of his booth

about his decision and go home. Alternatively, a button on the voting machine should be given in which there will be an option of not voting for any candidate. Any voter who does not wish to vote for any candidate may press this button to get his views recorded.

I think that these steps will improve youth participation in the electoral process.

Concluding Observations

To conclude, the right to vote is a precious political right that has been won through generations of hard struggle by millions of Indians. It is our responsibility to ensure that we judiciously exercise this right to strengthen Indian democracy. Many countries still do not have a representative democracy. The "Arab Spring" (2011-12) brought into sharp focus the spread of democratic consciousness in the Arab world. The Egyptians, for example, complained that they never had the freedom to choose their rulers. President Hosni Mubarak was forced to resign following mass protests. And then the people had to fight the military. Youth were in the forefront of the Egyptians' struggle for democracy. It is only in January 2012 that they voted in the historic first elections to the Egyptian parliament. But the new government did not last beyond a year because the Egyptian President, Mursi's misrule resulted in another popular uprising which ultimately led to a military coup.xxii

While the "Arab Spring" showed that there is increased awareness of the need for democracy in today's world, in India, political apathy, especially of the youth, is worrying everybody. Political apathy is dangerous for any democracy as it may strength the forces of fascism. In fact the recent Panchayat elections in West Bengal have revealed fascist tendencies in the ruling establishment which the State Election Commission has failed to curb. Opposition parties alleged attacks on them by the henchmen of the ruling party. Motorcycle rallies to intimidate candidates and voters alike, have been reported despite the ban on such rallies

by the State Election Commission. But the masses, in many places, put up stiff resistance to such politics of intimidation. The massive voter turnout in the elections shows that democracy in West Bengal is alive and vibrant.xxiii The youth have played an important role in this election.

Our young citizens should never be apathetic to voting in elections. They should remember Harold Laski's dictum that eternal vigilance is the price of liberty. Our young voters should take utmost care to exercise their franchise in the best interests of the nation. The Election Commission is sincerely trying to get more citizens to participate in the democratic process. Educational institutions, NGOs and the corporate sector have also pitched in to encourage our young citizens to vote. Political leaders of all hues should play an active role in inspiring young minds to vote. But, at the present moment, their deeds do not inspire our youth. Why is it that most of the seats reserved for leaders of political parties remained vacant at Vigyan Bhavan, New Delhi, where the main function of National Voters Day, 2012, was held on 25th January, 2012? One of the aims of the function was to bridge the distance between political parties and the youth, especially first time voters. But, thanks to the absence of political leaders, the effort of the Election Commission did not bear fruit.xxiv We do hope that our political leaders will realize the importance of National Voters' Day and help the Election Commission to politically socialize the new generation of Indians.

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NOTES

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